

APPLYING HO CHI MINH'S DIRECTION FOR POLITICAL POWER CONTROL IN VIETNAM NOWADAYS

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Abstract: Exercising and controlling power is to ensure that power is used for correct purposes, especially for powerful cadres and Party members, preventing the recession in morals, political thought and lifestyle of them - one of the dangers threatening regim and the Party. Therefore, during his revolutionary activities, Ho Chi Minh specially focused on political power control to prevent Party recession, contributing to making Party pure and strong as well as strengthen people's belief in the Party and authorities bodies at all levels. This article focuses on showing Ho Chi Minh's directions for exercising and controlling power in Vietnam nowadays.

Keywords: exercise; political power; Ho Chi Minh; Vietnam; nowadays.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ho Chi Minh's political power control ideology is a comprehensive and profound views system on foundation points including position, role, importance, purpose and meaning; forces, contents, methods, measures of controlling political power and promoting the role of organizations and offices in the political system as well as people's responsibility in this mission. Ho Chi Minh's ideology is still relevant, meaningful, and timely in today's world, which is the driving force behind the Communist Party of Vietnam's creation and application of it to control political power in Vietnam, contributing to the Party's building and correction, as well as the development of a strong and pure political system.

II. APPLYING HO CHI MINH'S DIRECTION

FOR POLITICAL POWER CONTROL IN VIETNAM NOWADAYS

A. Ho Chi Minh's Directions For Political Power Control

Firstly, Controlling political power from "inside". According to Ho Chi Minh, It is a technique of governing internal political system's organizations, and it is self management for each cadre or Party member, especially the leader holding an important position. For an organization, it is control of a group and individual in this internal organization. First, It is necessary to control power by rules, regulations, disciplines and national law. Charters, rules, regulations of the organization and the national legal system have to be built and updated incessantly. He required: "the law governed by the rule" and "unhonest people have to be punished by law, even if they are in any position or job". He directed and directly signed to introduce two Constitutions (1946, 1959), 16 laws, more than 1,300 sub-law documents with 243 decrees, regulations, governing all activities of the State and society.

Second, Control by self criticism and criticism; self control and controlling each other: Ho Chi Minh believed that: "...in the Party, in meetings for discussion, members listen to leaders reporting works, criticize weak points and elect comrades

in the executive board. It is a control based on the democratic centralism principle, criticism and self criticism, that the Party has to carry out strictly". The goal of self-criticism and criticism is to evaluate one's own strong and weak points, as well as the strong and weak points of others, in order to strengthen strong points and eliminate weak points, and to use strong points to correct the bads, the wrongs. To properly critique, the right methods and attitudes are required. Self criticism and criticism are implemented regularly, honestly and strictly; "must have comradeship, love each other", "do not criticize haphazardly and take no responsibility".

Third, Bottom-up and top-down control: Ho Chi Minh mentioned: "there are two methods of control. First method is bottom-up control, meaning that leaders control cadres' results. Another one is top-down control, meaning that citizens and cadres supervise leaders' mistakes and suggest solutions. This is the best way to control staffs". Bottom-up control means that: leaders' control for cadres' results". Top-down control has two levels: cadres' control for leaders and inferiority's control for superior; citizens' supervision for leaders. Inferiorities supervise superiors via democratic centralism principle, criticism and self criticism.

Fourth, Promoting appropriate authorities' role: Ho Chi Minh believed: " The Party and the government are taking on more and more responsibilities. To perform their duties effectively, Party Committees at all levels must strengthen supervision, requiring all Party members and officials to strictly implement Party policies. This is because supervision can encourage and educate members and officials to fulfill their duties and set a good example for citizens, then contributing to the Party's thought and organizations being strengthened. On inspection work, Ho Chi Minh affirmed: "Inspection work is a vital and honorable duty; it monitors and examines the strict execution of the direction, policies, resolutions and directives of the Party and the Government" "Officials' thoughts and behavior must be drastically altered in order to fulfill their responsibilities. We, as well as the inspection and other sectors, must carry out the Party's and government's programs resolutely and serve the people with utmost dedication."

Secondly, Ho Chi Minh emphasized Controlling political power from "outside". According to Ho Chi Minh, controlling power is based on citizens, they have the right to supervise power because they grant authority to the State. He mentioned meeting for debate, criticizing, expressing viewpoints, electing boards and councils as examples of forms: "In public, meetings for discussion, criticism, showing opinions and electing boards and councils are their way of control over leaders". He affirmed: " Law belongs to people, which is used to prevent harmful activities and protect the mutual benefits of most people". He saw it as a "head lamp" that assists leadership in being right and preventing high-handed problems among leaders at all levels: monitoring may enhance people's huge forces and positive attitude, raise awareness of officials' abilities and weak areas, and promote quick correction of errors.". According to him: " members speculating in the Party are unmasked thanks to supervision of people and the Party, making the Party become a model and being pure and to serve people with utter dedication. Revolution and all members become the model".

Besides, political power control is shown via promoting the role and strength of morals and self awareness in completing duties. Ho Chi Minh believed that the main reason for depraved political power is revolutionary morals recession and falling into individualism of cadres. Therefore, educating revolutionary morals to cadres and Party's members, making them become both leaders and faithful servants of people is the first solution because "public treasure only people having good behaviors and morals. Officials should be exemplary in order direct people"

Thirdly, inspection and supervision is specially focused. Inspection and supervision must be considered as the starting point and central stage in the Party's leadership approach to the State and the whole society. In order for inspection and supervision to contribute to effective power control, Ho Chi Minh required:"...Inspection committees and officials must study and be aware of the Party's lines and ideas, must constantly strive to improve their professional abilities, work hard, and nurture revolutionary principles. It is very important to strengthen one's sense of organization and discipline, as well as to honestly criticize and self-criticize in order to lead by example when it comes to disciplining, then supervision is conducted well. The leader must conduct self-inspection and organize a group of experienced officials to help the leader; At the same time, the inspector must uphold his work responsibilities with the spirit: "inspector has to take responsibility for what he inspect." Effective inspection and supervision contribute to preventing tyranny, abuse of power, corruption and drawbacks of cadres and Party members, threatening Party and regim. Ho Chi Minh emphasized that Party organizations, state agencies, the Fatherland Front, political and social organizations need to coordinate in inspecting and supervising to strengthen people's confidence in promoting strong points and correcting mistakes to make all of them happy and adrent as well as make progress.

B. Applying Ho Chi Minh's Direction For Political Power Control And Preventing Recession In Cadres And Party Members In Vietnam Nowadays.

Ho Chi Minh's ideology is the basic thought and the orientation of Vietnamese political systems activities in exercising power and preventing abuse of power leading to power corrupted during Party's leadership. Over the past years, the implementing the Resolution of the 12th Party Congress, the Resolutions of the 4th Central Committee of the XI and XII sessions on the work of Party building and rectification, the correct identification of power, the alienation of power, and control power to prevent, the deterioration of political ideology, morality, lifestyle, "self-evolution", "self-transformation" of party members and leaders have been deployed from central to grassroots levels. Along with the Party's policy of "continuing to build, complete and strictly implement the power control mechanism as well as prevent abuse of power and violation of discipline", according to the Resolution of the 12th National Congress, "The Party committee at all levels and organizations direct the inspection, improvement and strict implementation of the mechanism of inspection, supervision and control over the exercise of power. According to the Resolution of the 4th Plenum of the Central Committee, the 7th Plenum of the 12th Central Committee, "clearly define the authority and responsibility of collectives and individuals in each stage of work settlement and have sanctions to strictly handle violations"; at the same time, "build and perfect institutions to control power in cadre work on the principle that all powers must be strictly controlled by mechanisms; authority, must be bound by responsibility". The 12th Politburo's Regulation No. 205-QD/TW further emphasizes: tightening Party discipline, substantively implementing democracy, closely inspecting and supervising; sternly dealing with infractions against leaders, managers, and heads; requires each leading and managerial cadre to constantly improve, train, self manage and control themselves against the ambitions of power and the temptation of material interests in the face of alienation and "self-evolution" , "self-transformation" internally, etc. It has shown that power control is focused and gradually achieved initial results.

However, when facing the truth and accessing the reality of recession in a large group of powerful cadres, the Resolution of the 4th Central Committee of the 12th term clearly said: Many cadres and party members, including the leader, have not demonstrated their pioneering and exemplary character; instead, they have demonstrated bureaucracy and authority, which are not truly representative of reality and grassroots. Inspection, monitoring, and discipline by the party are not strict enough to deter, prevent the recession... Meanwhile, the deterioration of political ideology, morality, and lifestyle of a large number of cadres and party members has not been deterred, even be worse in some groups; corruption, wastefulness, and negativity are still serious, focusing on the number of party members in the state machinery. The registration and self-reflection follow 27 manifestations of degradation (9 manifestations of deterioration in political thought; 9 manifestations of deterioration in morality and lifestyle; 9 manifestations of "self-evolution", "self-transformation". " internally) according to the Resolution of the 4th Party Central Committee, term XII at all levels (through self-criticism and criticism, inspection and supervision) show that in somewhere, with delegated power, the recession of cadres and party leaders and managers, especially high-ranking cadres, is still going on, not only causing frustration among the people but also affecting the prestige of the Party.

From Ho Chi Minh's direction on controlling political power, in order to exercise control over power in the Party and political system effectively in Vietnam today, it is necessary to "organize a mechanism to control the exercise of power on the principle that all powers must be strictly controlled, the higher power, the greater responsibility" and implement general check, boost the people's role in supervision preventing abuse of power. 13th national party congress was hold with the goal of improving leadership ability and the Party's strength, building a pure and strong Party and political system, strengthening people's belief in Party and State,... the Party emphasized that the roles, positions, functions, tasks and powers of state agencies in the exercise of legislative, executive and judicial powers on the basis of the rule of law principles should be defined clearly and it is important to ensure that the State power is unified, have a clear division and closely coordinate and strengthen control over state power. In the next time, all levels need to focus on following methods:

Firstly, focusing on Party building and rectifying work. Resolution of the 4th Central Committee of the 12th Congress and Regulations No. 37-QD/TW, October 25, 2021 of the Central Committee on what Party members cannot do, Regulation 101-QD/TW of the Secretariat of the Party Central Committee (11th congress) on "The responsibility of setting an example of cadres and party members, especially main leaders at all levels", Regulation 55-QD/TW of the 12th Politburo on "Some tasks to do immediately to strengthen the role of cadres and party members" and Regulation No. 08-QDi/TW of the Central Committee Session XII on "The responsibility to set an example of cadres and party members, started from Politburo members, members of the Secretariat, members of the Central Committee" and Directive 05-

CT/TW of the 12th Politburo on "Promoting study and following Ho Chi Minh's thought, morality and style" are considered as primary solutions to inspect and supervise power of the Party and political system.

Secondly, focusing on improving the quality of thematic activities. The measures of self-criticism, criticism, inspection and supervision are conducted effectively, following the principle of closely combining "build and fight, establishment is the main", based on the registration of each Party Committee and individual on the prevention of recession and content of studying and following Ho Chi Minh's ideology, morality and style. Specifically, self criticism should be implemented regularly and strictly based on Ho Chi Minh's direction, supervision and inspection should be increased and principles of the Party should be implemented completely. Besides, the quality of self criticism, supervision and inspection should be improved thanks to principles of democracy, objectivity, honesty and completeness with increasing supervision in management and control over cadres and members under the supervision of the people and Party's members.

Thirdly, fight corruption and negativity resolutely and persistently, "must lock power in a cage of mechanisms and laws," continue to build and perfect the mechanism for controlling power, among Party leadership at all levels and between levels, from the top down and bottom up, ensures multi-dimensional control. Through tight norms and regulations, strengthen the supervision and inspection of cadres and party members for the exercise of authority in the Party. Control of power must be considered a Party discipline; ensure that the Party Committee, individuals in the Party Committee, and each leadership position have clearly defined functions, tasks, and powers; and publicize the rules and regulations on power control so that all cadres and party members must follow them without exception. Each agency, Party's organization and member also sets a good example in power control and follows rules of the Constitution, laws and the Party's regulations. At the same time, The Party must strengthen the mechanism of "self-control" through Party activities, self-criticism and criticism, through inspection, supervision, questioning and explanation activities from Party grassroots organizations to the Executive Committee Center; strengthen supervision of the exercise of power by state agencies and socio-political organizations; create a mechanism for organizations in the political system to re-monitor the exercise of power of cadres, party members and the Party along with rewards and strict discipline, then strengthen and increase the solidarity in each organization, agency and unit.

Fourthly, along with obeying regulation of Constitution, laws and Party disciplines, each cadre and Party member must self control as well as establish and practice the firm political stuff to *be steadfast* in Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh's thought, National independence and socialism goals and policies of renovation of the Vietnamese Communist Party; *be firm* in neglecting enchantment of power and preventing negative impacts caused by harmful news and activities of hostile forces; *be constant* in improving and to be imbued with revolutionary morals, implementing Integrity and public-spirited and selfless, preventing individualism, making efforts in studying to develop professional ability. It is important to fight against wrong behaviors, handle timely, remove cadres or Party's members who violate the laws and promote the role in setting a good example of leaders, managers and heads of agencies and units based on slogan "the higher authority, the more exemplary spirit" and the spirit of implementing Party's disciplines strictly.

III. CONCLUSION

Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control is a basic of thought and scientific reasoning elementary for Party's policies and viewpoints in building political systems and Party building and rectification; orienting supervision, inspection, prevention of corrupting power. Nowadays, recession in political thought and morals and corrupting power are burning in a large part of officials, causing severe impacts. During the arduous period of fighting against these problems, Ho Chi Minh's ideology showed its great value in building and rectifying a pure, strong and effective Party and political system.

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